

Priesthoods in Ptolemaic Thebes (Luxor)

By Lauren Dogaer, University of Basel

Entry tags: Funerary Beliefs and Rituals, Demotic Egyptian, Egyptian, Religious Group, Greek, Cult of Amun, Ancient Egyptian Religions, Language, Egyptian Religions, Egyptian (Ancient), Afro-Asiatic

The priesthoods in Ptolemaic Thebes (modern-day Luxor) consisted of several groups of religious personnel. The most important group of priests was the high clergy of Amun who worked in the temple of Karnak. Other groups of priests were attached to several temple and necropolis cults on the east bank, including the mortuary priests taking care of the mummification and mortuary cult of the deceased. Even though these various groups of priests are often seen as separate entities, many professional and personal connections existed between them.

Date Range: 400 BCE - 30 BCE

Region: Thebes (area)

Region tags: Luxor, Egypt, Africa, Thebes

Thebes is an ancient Egyptian city in Upper Egypt. The founding date is unknown, it is historically documented since the 11th dynasty. During the Middle Kingdom it became the capital of Egypt. Since the New Kingdom, the name "Waset" is documented, otherwise also Niut or Niut-reset. From the Greeks of the Ptolemaic period the name "Thēbai" (Thebes) has been preserved, but also the name "Diōs Pólis Megálē" (Great City of Zeus), from which in the time of the Roman Empire the names "Thebae" and "Diospolis Magna" were derived. Since at least the New Kingdom, the territory of Thebes included both sides of the Nile: Thebes-East and Thebes-West. Among the most important ancient sites in Thebes-West are the Valley of the Kings and the Valley of the Queens, Medinet Habu with the great temple of Ramses III, Deir el-Bahari with the mortuary temples of Hatshepsut and Mentuhotep II, as well as the Ramesseum. Thebes-East comprises the temples of Luxor and Karnak.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Birk, Ralph 2020. *Türöffner des Himmels: prosopographische Studien zur thebanischen Hohepriesterschaft der Ptolemäerzeit. Ägyptologische Abhandlungen 76.* Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz

– Source 2: Cannata, Maria 2020. Three hundred years of death: the Egyptian funerary industry in the Ptolemaic Period. Culture and History of the Ancient Near East 110. Leiden; Boston: Brill.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.trismegistos.org/arch/detail.php?quick=50>

– Source 1 Description: Webpage about the largest archive of Theban mortuary priests, including a detailed PDF-description about the archive

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://totenbuch.awk.nrw.de/>

– Source 1 Description: Webpage about the Book of the Dead and other funerary texts, including the Ptolemaic funerary papyri owned by the high clergy of Karnak

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.trismegistos.org/arch/>

– Source 2 Description: Webpage about the papyrus archives from Graeco-Roman Egypt, including the archives belonging to the mortuary priests from Ptolemaic Thebes

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Membership is default at birth for all types of Theban priests, although individuals could lose their membership if they did not obey the rules of the priesthood to which they belonged.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Whereas most individual high clergy priests held the same or similar titles as their fathers and therefore automatically performed certain functions (e.g. clothing the statue of the god) in the temple, there was also the possibility to hold certain titles for a shorter amount of time. They could apply for these positions, e.g. being the financial manager (lesonis) of the temple, and usually held them for one year. The priests working in the smaller cults on the east bank (e.g. in Deir el Medina, Deir el-Bahari, etc.) could also accumulate several liturgical days in the various cults. The mortuary priests automatically became mortuary priest by birth, but did have the choice to leave the priesthood.

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals belonging to the high clergy, the clergy working in the smaller temples and the mortuary priests did not have the option to switch between groups. A mortuary priest could not become a high clergy priest and vice versa. However, certain individuals seem to have been able to work in both temple and necropolis cults but they usually took care of the sacred living and deceased animals. Switching between classes was generally speaking not possible.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Notes: We can generally assume that individuals could start participating at a specific age. For the high clergy priests no direct evidence has been attested. For the mortuary priests on the other hand, we know that they became a member of their religious society at the age of 10 and they fully participated in the society's activities at the age of 16.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most members of the Theban priesthoods were male. Female high clergy members were often functioning as singers or sistrum-players. For the mortuary priests and the temple personnel working in the cults on the east bank, it seems female priests could also take care of the deceased and sell/buy liturgical days in the cults. The extent till which they actually performed the functions themselves is debated in the field.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– I don't know

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– I don't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: The high clergy priests were often paid in kind (e.g. offerings). These offerings were often paid for by the so-called royal syntaxis or subvention. This subvention was paid by the Ptolemaic government to the temples and could be used for the maintenance of the temple. Farmers and other individuals owning land, had to pay a certain amount of their harvest to the

government. Often parts of this harvest (e.g. wine) were directly paid by the farmers to the temple as part of the royal syntaxis. The priests could then use the wine for offerings and consequently for themselves.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: The religious infrastructure of the temple is paid for by the royal syntaxis or subvention of the Ptolemaic government. The priests had to officially apply for receiving refunds from the government, e.g. for the repairs of the sacred vessel used during festivals.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: The political officials are situated on a higher level than the religious officials. Financial controllers were often installed by the government in the temples, although these controllers could also be priests themselves. The dependence of the religious officials on the political officials is mainly financial.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Notes: During the Ptolemaic Period (and already before), people could also have other religions. Many Greeks lived in Thebes who had a different religion. No religion was ever enforced by the Ptolemaic government.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Notes: In Thebes, the local religious code is very often not following the polity legal code in detail. The local reality is very often more complex than the official reality portrayed by the government.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: Certain priesthoods (especially high clergy) were exempted from personal taxes as well as compulsory labor (e.g. every individual in Egypt had to move certain amounts of soil to keep the irrigation-system working)

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Important to note is that the scripture within the several sub-groups is not the same. The high clergy mainly left us funerary papyri written in hieratic or cursive hieroglyphs. Not all of them were able to write hieratic and hieroglyphs, this was reserved for the highly skilled scribes. No documentary texts (e.g. in the form of a temple archive) were found in the temple of Karnak, but they would mainly have been written in Demotic. Given the rather strict control from the Ptolemaic government over the temple finances, at least some high clergy priests will have been able to read/write Greek. The priesthoods working in the smaller temples as well as the mortuary priests mainly left us documentary texts in Demotic and Greek (in the form of personal/professional archives stored in tombs in the necropolis).

Are they oral:

– No

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The interpretation and composition of hieroglyphic (temple) texts was only done by a couple of highly skilled scribes. Therefore, no specific formal institution was responsible for this but a specific group within the religious group itself.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– No

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– I don't know

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: We do not have the actual settlement(s) preserved.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 800

Notes: The temple of Karnak.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 20

Notes: Some of the columns in the Hypostyle hall in Karnak are 20 meters.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: Many of the religious monuments (e.g. chapels dedicated to "smaller" gods) have not

been preserved so it is not possible to define the average religious monument in Ptolemaic Thebes.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: The Theban necropolis, which was the working area of the mortuary priests and some of the priests working in smaller cults (e.g. sacred ibis and falcon birds), was subdivided in several smaller necropoleis. The main area that was (re-)used during the Ptolemaic Period is located in the neighborhood of Deir el-Bahari (Assasif, Dra Abu al-Nagga, al-Khokha). Older tombs could be reused, but also new mudbrick (vaulted) tombs were built. They were mainly located at the beginning of the causeways leading towards Deir el-Bahari).

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: Several cemeteries were reused (Assasif, Dra Abu al-Nagga, al-Khokha, Sheikh abd al-Qurna, Qurnet Murai). Also new ones were built (e.g. at the entrance of the causeways leading up to Deir el-Bahari).

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the main temples still existed and were still in use (Deir el-Bahari, Medinet Habu, Karnak, Luxor). Others were newly build (e.g. the small temple of Medinet Habu, Deir el-Medina, Qasr al-Aguz). Many smaller sanctuaries and chapels were built as well.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Altars and especially libation installations were built for several gods. Especially the smaller shrines and sanctuaries will have contained altars.

↳ Devotional markers:

– I don't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Not one mass gathering point existed. Whenever a public religious festival took place the god was taken out of his shrine to be showed and the masses will have gathered outside the pylons of the temple.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– I don't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

Notes: But not only the public space. The most important and sacred iconography (and texts) were situated in the holy of holies of the temple, where the statue of the god was kept in his shrine. This sacred location was only accessible for the highest priests.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: An individual was made up of a ba (soul), ka (life force) and akh (what the individual becomes after death).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: In order for the deceased to live on in the afterlife, their body had to be preserved intact.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: The West is usually seen as the space beyond this world (which is why the tombs are often located on the west bank of the Nile). In addition, the underworld was located underground where the dead were buried.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife located in “other” space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– Yes

Notes: The mummification was done by the embalmers. Afterwards the cult of the dead was taken care of by the libation-pourers. The embalmers and libation-pourers together formed the group of mortuary priests.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– I don't know

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Many older tombs were reused during the Ptolemaic Period. Also family tombs were created, which meant people could be buried somewhere else at first and then moved to the family tomb.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: The grave goods could include objects used during the daily life of the deceased as well as objects especially made for the burial (the funerary equipment including funerary papyri, coffins, stelae, etc.). In case of the high clergy priests it is of interest that some of the ritual papyri they used during their lifetime in the temple could later on be turned into a funerary papyrus as part of their burial equipment. As far as we know, we only have burial equipment of high clergy priests. So far, no burials of members of the priesthoods working in the smaller temples and members of the mortuary priests have been found with certainty.

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: The grave goods could include objects used during the daily life of the deceased as well as objects especially made for the burial (the funerary equipment including funerary papyri, coffins, stelae, etc.). In case of the high clergy priests it is of interest that some of the ritual papyri they used during their lifetime in the temple could later on be turned into a funerary papyrus as part of their burial equipment. As far as we know, we only have burial equipment of high clergy priests. So far, no burials of members of the priesthoods working in the smaller temples and members of the mortuary priests have been found with certainty.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Especially for the high clergy.

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Not all members of the high clergy will have been buried with objects of significant wealth. Given the state of preservation as well as the lack of interest of early archaeologists almost no intact burials of the Ptolemaic Period have been recorded in a correct way. Therefore, it is difficult to distinguish between the various levels of wealth of these priesthoods.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god in Thebes during the Ptolemaic Period was Amun. The god had a couple of specific local manifestations. He was Kematef at Medinet Habu, Amenope at Luxor Temple, and Irita at Karnak. However, many of his aspects were merged with the god Osiris (the god of the underworld). This is called the process of Osirianization, which took place during the first millennium BC.

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Amenope (Amun of Luxor) had a chthonic aspect.

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - Yes

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Oracles for the god Amun could take place during certain festivals.

Whether this knowledge about an individual's future is only related to specific oracular questions or is related to general knowledge about that individual is unclear

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Thrice a day the daily ritual was performed for the god, in which he was washed, clothed and fed.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Many other gods were worshipped as well. Most of the high clergy priests were not only working in the cult of Amun, but also in the other Theban cults of Khonsu, Mut and Amenope (Amun of Luxor). In addition, many priests were working in the cult of Montu as well.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Yes
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
 - ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Theban Triad (Amun-Mut-Khonsu) was still important.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Geographically as in earlier periods.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

- ↳ Sacred object(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Many oaths were sworn at either the gate of Khonsu in Karnak or the small temple of Medinet Habu. These oaths were sworn in name of the god in front of a council of high clergy priests.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: The performance of rituals was very important. If the correct rituals were not performed, the order would be disturbed.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
 - I don't know

- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No

- ↳ Other [specify]
- I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
- Yes

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
- No

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
- Yes

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
- No

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
- No

- ↳ Other [specify]
- I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
- Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
- I don't know

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
- Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– I don't know

↳ Other [specify]
– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:
– No

Is an eschatology present:
– I don't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:
– Yes

Notes: The various groups of priests had their own social norms which they had to obey.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:
– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):
– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– I don't know

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: Ritual purity was only expected from the wab-(pure) priests. A wab was considered to be at the entry level of the high clergy.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: Priests were obliged to take care of their family members and to provide for them. Especially for women and elderly people.

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - I don't know
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: Karnak Temple Region
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– I don't know

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Priests had to clean themselves before entering a temple, especially after having had sexual intercourse.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: E.g. high clergy priests were not allowed to eat fish and for priests who on certain festival days drank wine in honor of the god, had a fixed amount of wine they were allowed to consume.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: All types of priests had to attend certain meetings, perform certain religious services at specific moments during the day. E.g. the high clergy had to perform the daily ritual during which the god was washed, clothed, fed etc. E.g. The mortuary priests had to pour the libations for the deceased in the necropolis every ten days.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: This seems to be only valid for individuals who were once part of the religious group. Afterwards they were marginalized. The priesthoods could, however, be in contact with many other members of society.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Various festivals were celebrated in Ptolemaic Thebes, of which the most important are the daily crossing of Khonsu-Shu (to provide bread for the deceased in the necropolis); the Decade Festival (a weekly celebration during which libations were poured for the deceased); the Opet and Valley Festivals (the two major Theban festivals in which Amun, but also Osiris, played an important role); the Chonsu

festival (the birth celebration of the local Theban child god); Khoiak festival (rituals performed for Osiris in the Osirian chapels in Karnak). The mortuary priests, and then especially the libation-pourers were involved in the Decade festival. The high clergy of Amun was participating in all of the festivals.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– I don't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– I don't know

Notes: It depends, various festivals and religious practices took place in which different types of priesthoods were involved. Depending on the festival the time interval would be different. Certain religious practices took place every day, every week or every year.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– I don't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– I don't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:
– I don't know

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: High clergy priests were not allowed to eat fish.

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: High clergy priests were typically bald

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the rank in priesthood different types of dress were allowed (e.g. the panther skin).

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, priests are taken care of in their old age. There was a support system in place for members of the high clergy, as well as for members of the association of the mortuary priests, which included elderly and female members.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The Theban priesthoods, and especially the high clergy, had to interact with the bureaucracy of the Ptolemaic government.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: They only provided food storage for their own group (priests). Public food storage was taken care of by the government.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: This is arranged by the government

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, water management was generally provided by the government.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Certain burial taxes (on the tombs and mummies) had to be paid to the temple. Also taxes for the usufruct of temple land (paid in wine or grain)

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Certain guardians were guarding the temple, but they did not function as a police force.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Several high clergy priests acted as judged in the so-called native court. In addition, also a Greek court existed. Not only court cases took place in the temple, but individuals could settle a dispute by swearing an oath for the local god in presence of the judges.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: With the Greek judges as well as with several Ptolemaic officials.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– I don't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: No legal code for high clergy priests from Thebes has been preserved, but several other legal codes from other regions have been found. Also the members of the association of the mortuary priests had to abide by the rules of the association. Therefore, a legal code was likely in place for all different ranks of priesthoods.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Hieratic and especially Hieroglyphic was confined to highly skilled scribes who were part of the high clergy. No distinct written language was confined to the priests working in the smaller temples and the necropolis. Demotic and Greek could be used by everyone.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Also the high clergy used Demotic and Greek

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: A religious calendar was in place, containing all the dates on which certain festivals took place.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They also used the "normal" Egyptian calendar, to which the religious calendar was also linked.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Tax payments by individuals owning temple land could be paid to the temple in kind (wine, grain etc.). This was used as offerings for the gods and subsequently to feed the priests.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Patorialism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Priesthoods in Ptolemaic Thebes (Luxor), Birk, Ralph. Türöffner Des Himmels: Prosopographische Studien Zur Thebanischen Hohepriesterschaft Der Ptolemäerzeit. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2020.

Reference: Priesthoods in Ptolemaic Thebes (Luxor), Cannata, Maria. Three Hundred Years of Death: The Egyptian Funerary Industry in the Ptolemaic Period. Leiden: Brill, 2020.

Reference: Priesthoods in Ptolemaic Thebes (Luxor), Klotz, David. Caesar in the City of Amun: Egyptian Temple Construction and Theology in Roman Thebes. Monographies Reine Élisabeth 15. Turnhout: Brepols, 2012.

Reference: Priesthoods in Ptolemaic Thebes (Luxor), Depauw, Mark. The Archive of Teos and Thabis from Early Ptolemaic Thebes: P. Brux. Dem. Inv. E. 8252-8256.. Monographies Reine Élisabeth 8. Turnhout: Brepols, 2000.

Reference: Priesthoods in Ptolemaic Thebes (Luxor), Pestman, Pieter Willem. The Archive of the Theban Choachytes (second Century B.C.): A Survey of the Demotic and Greek Papyri Contained in the Archive. Studia Demotica 2. Leuven: Peeters, 1993.

Reference: Priesthoods in Ptolemaic Thebes (Luxor), Quaegebeur, Jan. "Les Appellations Grecques Des Temples De Karnak". *Orientalia Lovaniensia Periodica* 6/7 (1975): 463-78.